

Unveiling the credence value: Consumer premium for pesticide-free practices in organic winegrowing

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ABSTRACT

The global rise in organic wine production and consumption reflects a growing consumer preference for environmentally sustainable options and a greater willingness to pay (WTP) compared to conventional alternatives. Despite this trend, few studies have isolated the specific influence of reduced synthetic pesticide use—a key criterion of organic certification—on consumer WTP. Existing research often treats organic production as a monolithic attribute, overlooking how consumers value specific practices, particularly in processed products such as wine. This study addresses this gap by estimating the contribution of pesticide-free practices to the overall WTP for organic wine and examining how this valuation varies based on knowledge, attitudes, and demographics. A reference price-dependent discrete choice experiment was conducted with 1,070 organic wine consumers across five Euro-Mediterranean wine-producing countries: France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain. The results show that up to 74% of the organic wine price could be attributed to pesticide-free practices, with notable heterogeneity across the five countries. Three distinct consumer segments emerged: *awareness-driven*, *certification-trusting*, and *price-sensitive*. These findings underscore the strong consumer preference for pesticide-free production and suggest that credible certification schemes and targeted marketing strategies could encourage pesticide reduction, even in conventional vineyards. Such efforts could support the sustainability goals outlined in the EU Green Deal and provide economic incentives for conventional winegrowers to transition toward more environmentally friendly practices.

1. Introduction

The intensive use of synthetic pesticides in agriculture poses a significant environmental and public health challenges, contributing to biodiversity loss, ecosystem degradation, and risk to human health (Finger & Möhring, 2024; Liviz et al., 2025; Tang et al., 2021). In 2021, global agricultural pesticide use reached 3.5 million tons of active ingredients, a 4% increase over the previous year, an 11% increase over the past decade, and a 100% increase since 1990 (FAO, 2023). The FAO reports on pesticide use and trade within the same period revealed that Europe's pesticide application slightly exceeded the global average on key metrics: per hectare (1.58 kg/ha), per agricultural value (0.92 kg/1000\$), and per person (0.65 kg/capita). These figures underscore sustainability concerns related to pesticide use in Europe's agricultural sector, highlighting the need for action. In response, the EU has set an ambitious goal under its Green Deal to halve pesticide use and associated risks by 2030 (Schneider et al., 2023; Wesseler, 2022). This goal, however, faces significant political and implementation hurdles (Finger

et al., 2024).

This study is situated within the context of growing interest in understanding how consumers can influence sustainable agricultural production through their consumption and purchasing behaviors (Santos-Corrada et al., 2024; Trudel, 2019). By increasing demand for certain products, consumers can incentivize more environmentally friendly production practices (Frehner et al., 2022; Vittersø & Tangeland, 2015). However, the extent to which consumers reward specific environmentally friendly agricultural practices—particularly within the value chains of highly processed foods—remains unclear, despite the growing preference for sustainable products such as organic foods (Malissiova et al., 2022). This ambiguity largely stems from the heuristic value often associated with sustainability labels (e.g., organic labels), which tends to overshadow specific production practices—a phenomenon commonly referred to as the "halo effect" (Borrello et al., 2024; Innerbichler et al., 2024). In the case organic products, the halo effect of organic labels often conceals the extent to which specific environmentally friendly farming practices influence consumer preferences and willingness to pay

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(WTP) a premium. Achieving clarity on the premiums that consumers place on specific practices under the organic umbrella is essential for creating market-based incentives that encourage conventional producers to adopt sustainability-aligned practices.

The organic wine industry offers an ideal context for examining consumer valuations of specific environmentally sustainable practices because of its dynamic growth, stringent production standards, and heightened environmental relevance. Over the past two decades, organic wine production and consumption have increased, with the global area under organic grape cultivation expanding nearly fivefold between 2004 and 2017 (Boncinelli et al., 2021). This growth reflects shifting consumer preferences driven by health concerns, environmental awareness, and trust in organic certifications (Jorge et al., 2020). Organic wines also command significant price premiums—ranging from 13% to 36% above conventional alternatives—highlighting consumers' willingness to pay for perceived added value (Scozzafava et al., 2021; Vecchio, Toccaceli, et al., 2023). Importantly, vineyards are among the most pesticide-intensive cropping systems in the EU Mediterranean region, requiring frequent chemical applications throughout the growing season (Chen et al., 2022; Liviz et al., 2025). As such, organic viticulture—which prohibits the use of synthetic pesticides—offers substantial environmental benefits and aligns directly with the EU Green Deal's goals for reducing pesticide use. This positions organic wine as not only economically significant but also a high-impact case for assessing consumer support for environmentally beneficial agricultural practices.

Organic wines under EU regulations are defined by certifications that mandate strict standards in both winegrape cultivation and winemaking practices (Provost & Pedneault, 2016; Reg. (EU), 2018). The cultivation guidelines emphasize the non-use of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers, while winemaking is restricted to natural methods with limited use of sulfites and other additives (D'Amico et al., 2016). Despite the growing demand for organic wines and the price premiums they command, existing research lacks clarity on how specific sustainable cultivation practices contribute to these premiums. Most studies examining consumer preference and WTP for organic wines have focused on broad factors such as health benefits, environmental concerns, biodiversity, sustainability perceptions, and sensory qualities. As a result, the organic attribute is often treated as a holistic concept, overlooking the specific production practices that influence consumer WTP (Boncinelli et al., 2021; Castellini et al., 2014).

One such overlooked factor is the role of pesticide-free practices, which are central to organic wine certification. To the best of authors' knowledge, few studies have directly examined the premium that consumers place on this specific attribute. For example, D'Amico et al. (2016) reported that consumers are willing to pay 20–50% more for organic wines labeled “no pesticides with sulfites.” However, their study did not isolate the independent contribution of pesticide-free practices to the overall price premium. Similarly, Zanchini et al. (2024) emphasized the influence of production methods on wine purchase decisions but did not identify the specific practices within organic, conventional, or biodynamic production that drive consumer preferences. Moreover, most research on WTP for pesticide-free attributes has focused on unprocessed organic products such as fruits and vegetables (Boccaletti, 2000; Hayati et al., 2017), leaving a significant research gap in understanding how this factor influences pricing in processed organic products such as wine. Addressing this gap is essential for clarifying how specific environmentally friendly practices—such as the reduction or elimination of synthetic pesticides—shape consumer WTP and the market price of organic wine. Such information could be used to incentivize conventional growers deterred by the bureaucratic nature of organic certification (Hauck et al., 2021) to adopt environmentally sustainable practices in line with the EU's green deal.

This study seeks to address this gap by evaluating the value organic consumers place on the reduced use of synthetic pesticides, a core requirement of organic certification, in their purchase decisions. We

hypothesize that reduced pesticide use significantly contributes to the price premiums of organic wines compared with other organic features by exploring three central questions: How much of the price premium for organic wines is attributable to the reduction in the use of synthetic pesticides? What distinct organic consumer segments exist on the basis of their valuation of pesticide-free practices in winegrape cultivation, and how does the willingness to pay for this attribute vary across the different segments? How do these consumer segments differ in terms of personal characteristics and their valuation of other organic wine attributes, such as price and certifications?

This study achieved its objective by employing a dynamic reference price-dependent discrete choice experiment (DCE) method. This DCE design uses the price and characteristics of consumers' previously purchased organic wines as a reference to estimate how much of their price premium is attributed to the reduced use of synthetic pesticides when they pay for organic wines. The approach enhances the realism of the choice design, particularly in the context of wine, where prices vary significantly across locations and over time (Kilders & Caputo, 2024).

The results have important implications for the policy, market mechanisms, and certification strategies needed to encourage the transition of conventional growers to more sustainable environmental practices. The findings are timely, highlighting how information on consumer rewards for pesticide-free practices could complement regulatory measures aimed at reducing pesticide use in agriculture under the EU Green Deal.

1.1. Background of organic regulation in the EU

Organic wines are made from organically grown grapes and cultivated without the use of synthetic products (in particular, pesticides and fertilizers) in viticulture. Instead, they rely on natural vine protection methods, such as sulfur, copper, plant extracts, and beneficial organisms that combat pests and diseases. Unlike conventional wines, organic winemaking prioritizes sustainability and ecological balance, ensuring a more natural and eco-friendly winemaking process (Borrello et al., 2024).

Organic regulatory standards for wine were established earlier in non-European countries than in Europe. This included countries such as the USA in 2002, Canada in 2009, New Zealand in the mid-1990s with the introduction of Sustainable Winegrowing New Zealand (SWNZ), and Australia, where standards evolved over time, formalized in the Export Control (Organic Goods) Rules 2021 (Castellini et al., 2014). Initially, the EU's approach was more limited, offering organic certification only for raw materials (grapes) rather than for the entire winemaking process. This changed in 2012 when the European Commission approved Regulation (EU) No. 203/2012, allowing organic certification of wines produced in line with certain specific standards outlined in the EU Organic Action Plan (Reg. (EU), 2012). The EU's organic regulations—Reg. No. 2007/834, 2008/889, later Reg. (EU) 203/2012, and currently Reg. (EU) 2018/848—covers all stages of production, preparation, and distribution. To qualify as organic, however, wines must primarily comply with restrictions in two critical areas, as shown in Fig. 1: viticulture (grape cultivation) standards and oenological (winemaking) practices. While both viticulture and oenological standards are integral to organic wine production, viticulture practices take center stage, particularly in promoting environmentally friendly production.

Against the backdrop of the practices prohibited in the production of organic wine compared with conventional variants, we review prior studies on consumer preferences and willingness to pay to inform our study hypotheses.

2. Literature and hypotheses

2.1. Factors influencing consumer preference and WTP for organic wine

Several empirical studies have attempted to identify the drivers of

Fig. 1. Organic wine regulation in the EU: key restrictive requirements at different production stages. Source: Authors' construct based on European Commission Reg. (EC) No 2007/834; Reg. (EC) No 203/2012; Reg. (EU) No 1308/2013; Reg. (EU) 2018/848 that regulate organic wine production.

consumer preference and WTP for organic wine (Katt & Meixner, 2020; Maesano et al., 2021). To provide an overview of the findings, we conducted a structured narrative review of relevant studies on consumers' willingness to pay and preferences for organic wines. Studies published between 2012 and 2025 were sampled from research databases, including Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus. The keyword combinations used include "organic wine preference", "willingness to pay", "consumer preference", "WTP premium", and "purchasing motivation" in English, French, German, and Spanish. The key factors examined in these studies were classified into four groups:

- a. Viticulture factors (VF): Those related to restrictions in grape cultivation (Fig. 1)
- b. Oenological factors (OF): Those under restrictions in oenological (winemaking) practices (Fig. 1)
- c. Intrinsic factors (IF): Those on consumer characteristics, such as knowledge, perceptions, attitudes, social norms, socio-demographics, etc.
- d. Extrinsic factors (EF): Those that involve external factors beyond viticulture and oenological restrictions, such as price, advertisements, brand, packaging, etc.

Table 1 summarizes the sampled studies and highlights the main drivers investigated. Most studies have focused primarily on intrinsic and extrinsic factors, whereas viticulture and oenological factors have not been explicitly analyzed. Instead, based on the variables examined, we infer that some studies indirectly capture aspects of VF and OF without directly addressing specific production practices, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

An exception is the study by D'Amico et al. (2016), which attempted to assess factors from all four categories. However, even in this case, the factor investigated under VF was not examined as an independent variable but as part of an interaction variable. In most other studies, any potential insights into the influence of viticulture and oenological practices consumer decisions could only be inferred.

This identified pattern aligns with findings from previous review

studies on the determinants of organic foods or wine purchase behaviors. For example, Katt & Meixner (2020) categorized the main drivers of consumers' WTP for organic foods into consumer-related, product-related, and purchasing-venue drivers, but cultivation and processing factors were not explicitly included. Similarly, Maesano et al. (2021) reported that socioeconomic and psychological factors, quality perceptions, sensory attributes, and taste influenced consumer decisions regarding organic wines without specifically addressing the role of viticulture and oenological practices in shaping these broad factors.

In summary, existing research has focused primarily on intrinsic and extrinsic factors—such as health perceptions, taste, price, and branding—while largely overlooking the direct impact of specific production practices. Viticulture attributes such as pesticide-free cultivation are often inferred rather than explicitly examined, leaving a gap in understanding how they influence consumers' willingness to pay a premium for organic wine.

2.2. Conceptual framework and hypotheses

Fig. 2 presents the conceptual framework of this study, illustrating the key factors influencing consumers' preferences and willingness to pay for organic wines, with a particular focus on their connection to pesticide-free practices. Notably, the main drivers shaping variations in consumer preferences and WTP include health concerns, environmental sustainability, sensory qualities, perceived risk, and consumer profiles. In the following sections, we develop the study's hypotheses by drawing on this framework, integrating insights from previous research and relevant theoretical foundations.

2.2.1. Drivers of consumer preference and the role of pesticide-free practices

One important driver of consumers' willingness to pay for organic wine is health consciousness, as organic wines are often perceived as healthier than conventional alternatives are (Bazzani et al., 2019; Bonn et al., 2016; Mann et al., 2012). Additionally, studies indicate that consumers believe that organically produced wines are not only

Table 1
Review of studies investigating the drivers behind WTP for organic wine.

Author and year	Region (Country)	Method	Factor identified or examined and classification	Classification remark
Moscovici et al. (2022)	Global	Logistic regression	-Wine knowledge ^c -Previous purchase (experience) ^c -Certification ^{a, b, s, d}	Primarily <i>EF</i> & <i>IF</i> , and some inferred <i>VF</i> & <i>OF</i>
Sogari et al. (2016)	Europe (Italy)	Cluster analysis	-Socio-demographics ^c -Certification ^d -Environmental protection ^{a, s, c}	Mainly <i>EF</i> & <i>IF</i> and inferred <i>VF</i>
Vecchio (2013)	Europe (Italy)	Ordinary least squares (OLS)	-Socio-demographics ^c -Consumption frequency ^c -Care about sustainability ^{a, s, c} -Knowledge specific claim ^c	Primarily <i>IF</i> and an inferred <i>VF</i>
Capitello et al. (2021)	Europe (Italy)	Discrete choice experiment	-Socio-demographics ^c -Label (quality, style, information) ^d -Brand ^d -Price ^d -Consumption frequency ^c -Place of purchase ^d -Socio-demographics ^d	Mainly <i>EF</i> & <i>IF</i>
Boncinelli et al. (2021)	Europe (Italy)	Discrete choice experiment	-Price ^d -Geographical indication ^{a, s, b, s, d} -Organic claim ^{a, s, b, *} -Producer popularity ^d	Primarily <i>EF</i> with inferred <i>VF</i> & <i>OF</i>
Szolnoki & Hauck (2020)	Europe (Germany)	Factorial analysis	-Social class ^c -Drinking frequency ^c -Attitude toward other organic products ^c -Socio-demographics ^c	Mainly <i>IF</i>
Rahman et al. (2014)	North America (USA-Washington State)	Sensory analysis	-Taste ^d -Appearance ^d -Attitude ^c	Mainly <i>EF</i> & <i>IF</i>
D'Amico et al. (2016)	Europe (Italy)	Ordered logistic regression	-PDO/PGI certification ^{a, s, b, s, d} - Brand ^d -Absence of sulfites ^b -Wine stopper type ^b -Taste ^d -Naturalness ^b -Environmental concerns ^{a, s, c} -Curiosity ^c -Insufficient information ^d -No pesticide with sulfites ^{a, b}	All factors examined but <i>VF</i> not independent
Jorge et al. (2020)	Europe (Italy)	Partial least squares-structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)	-Taste ^d -Health consciousness ^{a, s, b, s, c} -Eco-friendliness ^{a, s, c} -Tolerance ambiguity ^c -Socio-demographics ^c	Mainly <i>EF</i> & <i>IF</i> and inferred <i>VF</i> & <i>OF</i>
Sellers-Rubio & Nicolau-Gonzalbez (2016)	Europe (Spain)	Contingent valuation	-Knowledge ^c -Market segment ^d -Environmental concern ^{a, s, c} -Socio-demographics ^c	Mainly <i>EF</i> & <i>IF</i> and inferred <i>VF</i>
Borrello et al. (2024)	Europe (Italy)	Mixed methods	-Sustainability information (organic ^{a, s, b} * and fungus-resistant grape)	Inferred <i>VF</i> & <i>OF</i>
Dominici et al. (2025)	Europe (Italy)	Mixed methods	-Organic label ^{a, s, b, *} -Geographic indication (territorial brands) ^{a, s, b, s, d}	Mainly on inferred <i>VF</i> and <i>OF</i>
Dong & Gao (2024)	Not specified	Value-attitude-behavior model	-Values ^c -Attitudes ^c -Involvements ^c	Focused on <i>IF</i>

^a **VF (Viticulture Factors)** – Related to grape cultivation practices.

^b **OF (Oenological Factors)** – Related to winemaking practices.

^c **IF (Intrinsic Factors)** – Related to consumer traits, perceptions, and attitudes.

^d **EF (Extrinsic Factors)** – Related to external purchasing influences. [

* ⇒ although the study does not directly investigate the indicated factor, it is inferred based on the rationale behind the variable]

beneficial to the environment but also superior in quality (Rahman & Chen, 2025). The WTP for organic wines is further influenced by their eco-friendly production methods and adherence to sustainable agricultural practices (Bonn et al., 2016; Maesano et al., 2021).

In addition to health and environmental concerns, consumers often view the “organic” label as a risk-reduction cue, choosing organic wines to minimize potential risks associated with conventional wine production, such as exposure to synthetic chemicals (Dong & Gao, 2024; Ogbeide et al., 2015). Moreover, WTP for organic wines is often driven

by trust in eco-certifications and consumer profiles, including demographic, socioeconomic, and attitudinal characteristics (Moscovici et al., 2022; Schäufele & Hamm, 2017; Vecchio, Toccaceli, et al., 2023).

A closer examination of these key drivers suggests that many of the drivers of consumer preferences for organic wines could be associated with the reduced use of synthetic additives and chemicals in wine production. For example, health, environmental, risk, and sustainability concerns are often linked to pesticide-free practices, which minimize the amount of chemical residues—such as fungicides—detected in

Fig. 2. Conceptual framework of the study: what determines consumer WTP for organic wines and the link to non-use of synthetic pesticides and other requirements. Source: Authors' own construct based on the literature.

conventional wines (Liviz et al., 2025; Pérez-Mayán et al., 2021).

However, despite strong consumer support for organic wines and extensive research on the determinants of WTP premiums, the exact portion of the price premium specifically attributable to the reduced use of synthetic pesticides—rather than other organic attributes—remains unclear. Prior studies suggest that WTP for organic wines is strongly associated with concerns about health risks and environmental sustainability (Nitzko et al., 2024a; Santini et al., 2013), which are closely tied to the reduction of chemical pesticides in grape cultivation. Therefore, we infer that the limited use of synthetic pesticides in organic winegrowing accounts for a significant proportion of consumer premiums and propose the following hypothesis:

H1. A significant proportion of the price premium for organic wines is attributable to the limited use of synthetic pesticides in winegrape production compared to other organic requirements.

2.2.2. Consumer segmentation based on valuation of pesticide-free practices

Consumer preferences for organic wine are diverse, with varying estimates of the WTP premium and influencing factors reported in the literature (Brugarolas Mollá-Bauzá et al., 2005; Schäufele & Hamm, 2017; Vecchio, Annunziata, et al., 2023). For some consumers, eco-certifications and environmental considerations are key drivers of organic wine purchases, whereas for others, price plays a more significant role (Modica et al., 2025).

Despite numerous studies indicating a greater consumer preference and WTP for organic wines than for conventional wines, some research presents contrasting findings. Schmit et al. (2013) and Abraben et al. (2017) suggest that certain consumers associate organic wine labels with lower quality or perceive them as offering less value for money. Similarly, Delmas and Lessem (2017) reported that consumers tend to prefer organically labeled wines over conventional options only when the price is lower (Boncinelli et al., 2021).

The varying determinants and conflicting findings underscore the segmentation and heterogeneity in consumer preferences for organic wine (Boncinelli et al., 2021; Zanchini et al., 2024). Thus, while some consumers may prioritize sensory attributes such as taste, others are more driven by extrinsic environmental factors, including pesticide-free practices. This suggests that although organic wine consumers may share similar motivations to some extent, their valuation of

pesticide-free practices would likely differ. On this basis, we hypothesize the following:

H2. Distinct consumer segments exist based on their valuation of pesticide-free organic production practices.

2.2.3. Consumer segments and their characteristics

Research indicates that consumer behavior toward organic wine is shaped by demographic, socioeconomic, and attitudinal characteristics, all of which influence both WTP and preference formation (Moscovici et al., 2022; Schäufele & Hamm, 2017). For instance, Moscovici et al. (2022) identify age as a key factor, with younger consumers being more willing to pay a premium for organic wines. Similarly, Barber et al. (2009) reported that consumers are more likely to purchase eco-friendly wines and pay a higher price when they are informed, educated, and made aware of the product's environmental benefits. Additionally, Schäufele and Hamm (2017) reported that increased knowledge of sustainable wine production enhances consumer preference for such options.

These findings suggest that personal traits—such as demographics, attitudes, and knowledge—are crucial moderating factors influencing consumer WTP for organic wines. Consumers with greater environmental awareness are more likely to prioritize sustainable winegrowing practices, such as reduced pesticide use, whereas price-sensitive consumers may focus more on affordability and place less emphasis on pesticide reduction. Furthermore, factors such as country of residence, economic status, trust in certifications, and perceptions of pesticide use could further shape how consumers value pesticide-free practices, leading to distinct consumer segments (Bonn et al., 2016; Ogbeide et al., 2015). Consequently, we hypothesize the following:

H3. Consumer segments, based on their valuation of pesticide-free practices, also differ significantly in terms of personal characteristics and their assessment of other organic wine attributes, such as certifications and price.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Data collection and study region

The data for this study were obtained from the Qualtrics consumer research panel as part of the broader EU Horizon 2020 NOVATERRA

project, which aims to understand consumer support for pesticide reduction. The Qualtrics panel is built through a rigorous recruitment process using multiple channels, including email invitations, social media, and website pop-ups, with participation incentivized by rewards such as gift cards or discounts. Panelists provide detailed demographic and behavioral information upon joining, ensuring targeted survey distribution. To maintain engagement and data accuracy, Qualtrics employs regular communication, profile updates, and strict compliance with data protection regulations.

To ensure a balanced and representative sample, the study used stratified sampling on the basis of sex and age. The age distribution of the respondents was 11.47% for 18–24 years, 16.83% for 25–34 years, 17.99% for 35–44 years, 19.55% for 45–54 years, and 34.16% for 55 years and older. Gender representation was nearly equal, with 49.50% male and 50.50% female respondents. Additionally, efforts were made to achieve balanced representation across countries. The key eligibility criterion was that participants must have purchased wine within the three months preceding the survey.

For this study, an additional criterion required that the purchased wine be organic. This, combined with the demographic quotas, resulted in an incidence rate of 60%—indicating the proportion of the general population that met the specific participation criteria—ensuring a relevant and high-quality sample.

The study focused on five Mediterranean EU member states, among the top consumers and producers of organic wine (OIV, 2023). France, Greece, Italy, and Spain rank among the world's top 10 organic wine producers, accounting for more than 90% of the EU's organic vineyard area (OIV, 2021). These countries are also part of the NOVATERRA project, which aims to reduce pesticide use in vineyards and olive groves by developing alternatives capable of reducing pesticide use (<http://www.novaterraproject.eu/>).

The total number of participants recruited based on the screening criteria was about 1,400 organic wine consumers. However, after data quality checks, the final sample size was reduced to 1,070. To ensure a consistent understanding across countries, the survey instrument was initially designed in English and then translated into each country's native language with input from wine experts. A pre-test involving 15 participants per country was conducted to ensure clarity before the full survey was implemented. This process involved assessing question comprehension, response consistency, and survey flow while identifying potential fatigue issues. Feedback from the pre-test led to minor refinements before full-scale data collection, ensuring the instrument's reliability across different linguistic and cultural contexts. Data collection took place from July 5 to August 9, 2024, while the overall study process, including design and pre-testing, spanned from April to August 2024. Conducting the survey within a short timeframe, outside major seasonal promotions, helped minimize the impact of price fluctuations on consumer responses.

Participation was voluntary, with informed consent obtained, and ethical approval was granted by the Ethics Committee of the Centre for Agro-Food Economy and Development (CREDA) (Approval No. O20-2024). The study complied with GDPR regulations, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality.

3.2. Survey approach

The study employed the discrete choice experiment (DCE) approach to achieve its objectives, leveraging its ability to capture individuals' marginal utility by analyzing the trade-offs they make between various product attributes when making purchase decisions. This method is particularly well suited for products such as wine, which has numerous attributes influencing consumer preferences (Mazzocchi et al., 2022). The DCE method is based on Lancaster's choice theory, which assumes that consumers act rationally and seek to maximize utility. Originally applied to predict the proportion of consumers willing to try new food products in a fast food restaurant by Louviere in 1984, the DCE has since

become a leading stated preference method in the food sector. It is widely used to identify key attributes that influence consumer preferences. The method uses a survey questionnaire to create hypothetical market scenarios (choice sets) that simulate purchase decisions on the basis of alternatives that vary in terms of quality attributes and price (Contini et al., 2019). The subjects are presented with a set of alternatives, each comprising different combinations of attribute levels, including price, enabling the monetization of the value of each attribute. This allows them to choose the option that best meets their needs, taking into account the trade-offs between various attributes.

The survey questionnaire was divided into three sections. The first section included filter questions to ensure that the participants met the qualifications for the study, gathering information such as gender, country of residence, age, past wine purchase history, and satisfaction with previous purchases. The second section focused on the main choice experiment to evaluate consumer valuation of the key attributes. The final section collected further sociodemographic information, as well as consumer perceptions and knowledge about pesticide use in wine production.

3.3. Reference price-dependent choice design

To estimate consumers' willingness to pay for pesticide avoidance in organic wine, we implemented a dynamic reference price-dependent design. This approach anchors hypothetical alternatives to each respondent's most recent organic wine purchase—typically 100% pesticide-free—creating realistic trade-offs by varying pesticide levels and offering lower prices relative to their reference wine.

Methodologically, this aligns with pivot designs in discrete choice experiments (Hensher, 2004; Hensher & Greene, 2003; Rose et al., 2008), which adjust attribute levels relative to a reference point. However, unlike traditional pivot designs that rely on population averages (e.g., Bansal & Daziano, 2018) or segmented reference groups (e.g., Contini et al., 2019), our design is pivoted on individual-level reference points, requiring a two-stage setup. In stage one, the respondents provided detailed information about their most recent organic wine purchase (e.g., brand, origin, price, taste). In stage two, this information was dynamically integrated into the choice tasks.

The design ensured that participants compared alternatives to a familiar baseline, enhancing realism and contextual relevance. All other wine attributes remained fixed, allowing us to isolate the premium attributed to reduced pesticide use, different certification regulators, and price. This setup leverages reference point theory (Hess & Rose, 2009; Kim et al., 2020), which holds that consumers evaluate new choices relative to past experiences and not in isolation.

By tailoring choice sets to each respondent, the design accommodated regional price variation, minimized hypothetical and attribute-selection bias, and improved the validity of inferred preferences—particularly in a product category like wine, where prices and perceived quality vary widely.

3.4. Attributes and levels in choice design

The dynamic reference price-dependent choice approach enables us to consider a broad range of relevant organic wine attributes while focusing on the key attributes on the basis of the study objectives. In the first step, the respondents validated 14 attributes—such as taste, origin, and vintage—that influenced their most recent (reference) purchase, forming the basis for the choice task. Accordingly, the final design incorporates three attributes—(i) reduced pesticide use, (ii) certification, and (iii) price—all of which are critical signaling attributes for organic wine (Fanasch & Frick, 2020).

Reduced pesticide use: To evaluate consumers' valuation of the limited use of synthetic pesticides in organic winegrowing, we presented wines made from grapes that varied in terms of the percentage volume of synthetic pesticides applied by winegrowers. Given that participants had

previously purchased organic wine—assumed to be made from 100% pesticide-free organic grapes—the alternatives featured varying levels of pesticide use relative to the organic reference. Four levels of the pesticide reduction attribute were included, expressed as the percentage volume of synthetic pesticides avoided during grape cultivation relative to standard conventional practices (see Table 2). The four levels of the pesticide reduction attribute were based on pesticide-reducing technologies developed under the NOVATERRA project, which were shown to reduce the percentage volume of pesticide use in vineyards by up to 40%.

Certification: Certification in the wine industry, particularly for organic wine, serves as a crucial signal to consumers. It confirms quality, transparency, health, and safety, helping consumers make more informed decisions (Delmas & Lessem, 2017; Parga Dans et al., 2019). The EU's organic regulation mandates a special logo for organically certified wines, including those imported from non-EU countries. Wines not made from 100% organic grapes are prohibited from displaying the EU organic logo. In the EU, organic certification is granted by authorized certifiers, which may be an EU-approved third-party body, independent third-party agencies, or first- and second-party organizations such as the participatory guarantee system (Cuéllar-Padilla & Ganuza-Fernandez, 2018; Fanasch & Frick, 2020; Fouilleux & Loconto, 2017; Iannucci & Sacchi, 2022). Therefore, our design incorporated a four-level certification attribute to reflect the different certification systems to ascertain which certification system provided a trusted signal to consumers regarding sustainable prices in wine production. The certification levels include no certification (NC), where wines carry no form certification logo; independent certification (IC), provided by independent third-party regulatory bodies to ensure compliance with production standards; participatory certification (PC), a locally driven, first- or second-party certification based on stakeholder participation, trust, and knowledge exchange; and EU-approved certification (EC), issued by agencies authorized by the European Commission or national governments to verify compliance with organic or sustainable regulations.

Price: To estimate the monetary value of the attributes in the design, we included a four-level price attribute expressed as percentage reductions relative to the price of the reference organic wine. Since the reference wine was organic and made from 100% pesticide-free grapes, the four price levels represented 5%, 15%, 30% and 50% less than the reference price, accounting for the four levels of the "reduced pesticide use" attribute compared with the price reference organic wine.

The direct inclusion of only three attributes of interest allows respondents to focus on salient signals and to reduce the potential of attribute non-attendance (ANA), a behavioral phenomenon where respondents ignore certain attributes during decision-making (Colombo et al., 2013; Hensher et al., 2005). Other factors (e.g., taste, brand, origin) were captured via a reference wine—based on each respondent's most recent organic purchase—which served as a fixed baseline. This design preserved real-world context, isolated valuations of pesticide reduction and certification, and minimized the cognitive load on participants.

3.5. Implementation of the choice design

The study employed an unlabeled efficient design using Ngene© 1.3 software to optimize the combination of attribute levels for the choice sets. Based on the three attributes, each with four levels, an optimal efficient design for estimating main effects requires a minimum of 12 choice sets, given the number of parameters to be estimated. However, to ensure a realistic choice design, we imposed additional constraints. For example, higher levels of pesticide reduction were only allowed to be combined with price levels closer to the reference price (i.e., the respondent's previously purchased organic wine) and vice versa, to minimize the number of dominants in the choice situations. The incorporation of these realism-enhancing constraints while maintaining high statistical efficiency required expanding the design to 16 choice sets. The

final optimal efficient design, generated with non-informative priors, was achieved at evaluation 449, yielding a D-error of 0.149 and a D-optimality of 83.3%.

The 16 choice sets were divided into two blocks of 8 choice sets each to reduce the cognitive burden on respondents and to ensure that the task remained manageable. Each choice set included three alternatives: two unlabeled hypothetical wine options with varying combinations of the three attributes and an opt-out option representing the respondent's previously purchased organic wine ("None of these" or "I prefer my last purchase"). Fig. 3 provides an example of the choice set cards shown to respondents during the survey.

As stated preference methods such as DCEs are inherently prone to hypothetical and social desirability biases, the study used both "solemn oath" and "cheap talk" scripts at the beginning of the choice experiment (Carlsson et al., 2005; De-Magistris & Pascucci, 2014; Krumpal, 2013). These scripts have been shown to help align attitudes and intentions in hypothetical scenarios with real-life situations (Ajzen et al., 2004). The solemn oaths and cheap talk scripts¹ used at the start of the survey are shown in the footnote below.

3.6. Data analysis

3.6.1. Estimating WTP for pesticide-free practices in organic wine production

To estimate the proportion of the organic price premium attributable to reduced pesticide use (Hypothesis 1), we employed the Random parameter logit (RPL) model. This model is suitable for capturing consumer preference heterogeneity, random taste variation, and correlations in unobserved factors—making it ideal for modeling complex decision-making behaviors (Glenk et al., 2024; Waseem et al., 2019).

Based on the Random Utility Theory (McFadden, 1974), the utility (U_{ij}) that individual i derives from choosing alternative j is composed of a deterministic component (V_{ij}) and a stochastic error term (\mathcal{E}_{ij}):

$$U_{ij} = V_{ij} + \mathcal{E}_{ij} \quad (1)$$

Here, V_{ij} represents the observable part of utility, typically a linear function of the attributes of the alternatives in the choice task, whereas \mathcal{E}_{ij} captures the unobservable influences. Assuming rational choice, the probability that individual i prefers alternative j over alternative k can be expressed as:

$$P(U_{ij} > U_{ik}) = P(V_{ij} - V_{ik}) > (\mathcal{E}_{ik} - \mathcal{E}_{ij}); \forall j \neq k \in S \quad (2)$$

where S is the choice set of J alternatives, $j = 1, \dots, J$.

In the RPL framework, the vector of preference coefficients (β_j) is allowed to vary randomly across individuals and is drawn from a specified distribution (e.g., normal or lognormal). The deterministic component V_{ij} is typically specified as a linear-in-parameter function:

$$V_{ij} = \beta_1 \times \text{PesticideFree}_{-ij} + \beta_2 \times \text{CertificationType}_{-ij} + \beta_3 \times \text{Price}_{-ij} + \gamma * \text{ASC}_{-ij} \quad (3)$$

where $\text{PesticideFree}_{-ij}$ and Price_{-ij} are continuous variables; $\text{CertificationType}_{-ij}$ is a categorical variable (with 'no certification' as the base

¹ **Cheap talk script:** Attention! Research indicates that people often behave differently when making hypothetical decisions than in real-life situations, creating a gap between stated intentions and actual behavior in markets. For this experiment, we ask you to make your decisions as if you were making a real purchase—bearing in mind that you would pay for the wine and take it home. Please carefully consider which wine alternative you would buy, based on the level of synthetic pesticides avoided, the certification authority, and price relative to your last purchased organic wine. Please confirm your agreement: **Solemn Oath script:** I, the consented participant of this experiment, do accept that during this experiment, I will tell the truth and always provide honest answers. Do you agree? Yes/No

Table 2
Attributes and level definition.

Attribute	Definition	Base	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Reduced pesticide use	The percentage of spray volume of pesticides reduced by winegrowers compared to standard conventional practice	-10%	-20%	-30%	-40%
Certification	Regulatory bodies that issue certificates to signal compliance with accepted organic practices	Non-certification (NC)	Participatory certification (PC)	Independent third-party certification (IC)	EU-approved third-party certification (EC)
Price	Price expressed as a percentage of the 750 ml bottle of organic red wine most recently purchased	-5%	-20%	-35%	-50%

Fig. 3. Sample of choice card. [Note: This follows a first stage where details about the most recently purchased organic wine were collected. For example, when a consumer indicated that the price of the last wine (XX) was 4.00 €, the prices displayed for Option1 and Option2 are 3.80€ and 3.20€, which are 5% and 20% less, respectively as shown by the choice card].

category); ASC_{ij} represents an alternative specific constant; and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3,$ and γ are parameters to be estimated.

The alternative specific constant captures the preference for alternative j among all J alternatives. In this study, the ASC takes a value of one (1) if either of the two hypothetical wines with partial levels of pesticide avoidance (i.e., options 1 and 2 in Fig. 3) is selected and zero (0) if the reference alternative is chosen. The ASC, therefore, measures consumers' willingness to switch from their reference wine (organic wine) to the hypothetical options based on the level of pesticide reduced, price, and certification, ceteris paribus.

The price attribute in the choice model facilitates the estimation of premiums associated with changes in other attribute levels. The willingness to pay for a given attribute represents the monetary value that consumers assign to a unit change in that attribute. It is calculated as the negative ratio of the partial derivative of the utility function with respect to the attribute of interest divided by the partial derivative of the utility function with respect to the price variable (Van Loo et al., 2011). Based on the specified RPL model in eq. (3), consumer WTP for an attribute, for

example, reduced pesticide use, is estimated as:

$$WTP_{PesticideFree} = - \frac{\partial V_{ij} / \partial (PesticideFree)}{\partial V_{ij} / \partial (Price)} = - \frac{\beta_1}{\beta_3} \tag{4}$$

In this study, we report unconditional WTP estimates, which are derived from the sample-level mean coefficients of the estimated RPL model. These estimates represent the average consumer WTP, assuming that the preference distribution applies to all individuals. Although conditional WTP, which is derived by conditioning on an individual respondent's choices, provides personalized estimates and valuable individual-level insights, unconditional WTP offers a broader, more generalizable measure of consumer valuation across the entire sample. This makes unconditional WTP particularly useful for capturing overall market trends and informing policy and business decisions based on aggregate consumer preferences.

3.6.2. Exploring consumer heterogeneity using the latent class model (LCM)

To further explore heterogeneity in consumer preferences

(Hypotheses 2 and 3), we employed a Latent Class Model (LCM). Unlike the RPL model, which assumes continuous heterogeneity in preferences, the LCM assumes that individuals belong to a finite number of unobserved (latent) classes, each with its own set of preference parameters (Greene & Hensher, 2003). The LCM thus captures preference heterogeneity by modeling it as a discrete distribution, using endogenous segments based on unobserved differences in consumer preferences.

Following Gonçalves et al. (2020), the probability that individual i in class c chooses alternative j in choice situation t , conditional on the preferences within each class, is as follows:

$$P_{ijt|c} = \frac{\exp(\beta_c X'_{ijt})}{\sum_i \exp(\beta_c X'_{ijt})} \quad (5)$$

where β_c is the vector of parameters determining class membership for class c and where X_{ijt} includes sociodemographic and attitudinal variables (e.g., age, income, health concerns, and knowledge of pesticide use). The probability that individual i belongs to a particular class is given by Eq. (6) (Gonçalves et al., 2020; Greene & Hensher, 2003):

$$P_{ijt|c} = \frac{\exp(\delta_c Z_i)}{\sum_{c \in C} \exp(\delta_c Z_i)} \quad c = 0, \dots, C, \delta_c = 0 \quad (6)$$

where the C^{th} vector is normalized for model identification purposes, δ_c represents class-specific parameters and Z_i represents a vector of attributes and individual characteristics. Within each class, utility is modeled as a function of the choice attributes, similar to the logit form specified in eq. (3).

Consequently, the probability that an individual i chooses alternative j in a given choice situation t is as follows:

$$P_{ijt} = \sum_{c=1}^C P_{ic} \times \prod_{t=1}^T P_{ijt|c} \quad (7)$$

where:

Π is the probability of class membership for class c , and $P_{ijt|c}$ is the choice probability conditional on membership in class c .

This probability is derived by maximizing the following log-likelihood function for the sample:

$$\ln L = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \gamma_{ijt} \ln \left(\sum_{c=1}^C P_{ic} \times \prod_{t=1}^T P_{ijt|c} \right) \quad (8)$$

where $\gamma = 1$ when alternative j is chosen and 0 otherwise.

Determining the number of latent classes is critical and requires careful consideration. The appropriate number of classes is often determined using criteria that balance model fit and complexity, such as the Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC) (Konishi & Kitagawa, 1996; Scarpa et al., 2009). The general specification of the information criterion is given by $C=2L+kJ$, where L is the value of the log-likelihood function at convergence, J is the number of estimated parameters in the model, and k is a penalty constant (Scarpa et al., 2009). The AIC is obtained when $k=2$, and the Bayesian information criterion is obtained when $k=\ln(N)$. The BIC is generally reliable, as it avoids biases inherent in the AIC that could lead to overestimation of the number of classes (Weller et al., 2020). In this study, the BIC is used to determine the class solution with further confirmation provided by the AIC statistics.

The study used NLOGIT version 6 to estimate both the LCM and RPL choice models. The NLOGIT software, developed by Greene (2018), is specialized for estimating discrete choice models with flexibility for complex models.

3.6.3. Dealing with country-specific differences

Due to cultural, economic, and regional differences that may influence consumer preferences and behavior across the five countries in our

study, we implemented additional measures to account for cross-country variation. First, we included country-specific dummy variables in both the pooled RPL and LCM models. These dummies served as categorical controls by allowing the estimation of separate intercepts for each country. We also interacted the country dummies with the alternative-specific constant, which equals 1 if a respondent chose one of the hypothetical wines (Option 1 or 2), and 0 if they chose their reference wine. These interaction terms captured the influence of unobserved, country-specific factors—outside the scope of the experimental design—on consumers' likelihood of switching from their reference wine to a hypothetical option. By omitting its dummy variable in the estimation, France was used as the reference country. This decision was based on France's role as a mature and prominent market for organic wine, with high consumer awareness of and engagement in pesticide-free agricultural practices (Alonso Ugaglia et al., 2021; Hauck et al., 2021). Using France as a baseline allowed for a meaningful comparison of consumer preferences in the other countries.

In addition, we estimated separate RPL models for each country to better capture heterogeneity in preferences and WTP for organic wine attributes. Although the coefficients from these country-specific models are not directly comparable owing to potential scale differences in utility functions—resulting from variation in error term variances and data distributions (Swait & Louviere, 1993; Poe et al., 2005)—they offer deeper insights into country-level consumer dynamics.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Among the 1,070 valid responses from organic wine consumers who participated in the choice experiment, 52% were male, and 48% were female². In terms of age distribution, 13% of the participants were between 18 and 24 years of age, 22% were between 25 and 34 years, 21% were between 35 and 44 years, 18% were between 45 and 54 years, and 26% were over 55 years of age. The participants were distributed across the five countries as follows: 26% from France, 23% from Greece, 27% from Italy, 8% from Portugal, and 17% from Spain. Most participants (99%) had at least a secondary education, and over 68% lived in cities with populations exceeding 50,000. More than 70% were gainfully employed, either as employees or business owners, and over 80% reported being primarily responsible for purchasing wine. In terms of purchase frequency, 16% of the consumers were low-frequency buyers (purchasing organic wine less than four times a year), 53% were medium-frequency buyers (purchasing four to eight times a year), and 31% were high-frequency buyers (purchasing more than nine times a year). Overall, the sociodemographic profile of the respondents closely aligned with that of wine consumers reported in similar studies (Parga-Dans et al., 2023).

Based on the consumers' responses regarding their knowledge of pesticide use in vineyards for grape cultivation, as presented in Table 3, we categorized the respondents into four groups reflecting their subjective knowledge of pesticide use in winegrowing. Notably, despite the reduced use of synthetic pesticides being a key practice in organic wine production, over half of the consumers (55%) reported having little to no knowledge of pesticide-related practices in winegrowing. This limited awareness among a significant proportion of organic wine consumers suggests that their purchasing decisions may be influenced more by factors other than the limited use of synthetic pesticides.

Similarly, consumer attitudes toward pesticide use varied, with 18.1% indifferent and 81.9% expressing concern at different levels. While 28.2% reported slight concern, 21.1% were moderately concerned, and 32.5% had high to extreme levels of concern. This suggests

² For this study, gender is defined in binary terms—male and female—based on participants' self-reported responses.

Table 3
Descriptive statistics of the participants (N=1,070).

Characteristics	Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	515	48.1
	Female	555	51.9
Age	18-24 years	140	13.1
	25-34 years	231	21.6
	35-44 years	229	21.4
	45-54 years	192	17.9
	55+ years	278	26.0
Country	France	281	26.3
	Greece	246	23.0
	Italy	286	26.7
	Portugal	80	7.5
	Spain	177	16.5
Employment	Working	755	70.6
	Unemployed	315	29.4
Education	Primary school	11	1.0
	Secondary school	120	11.2
	Postsecondary	356	33.3
	University level +	583	54.5
Place of residence	A city <50,000	465	43.5
	A city > 50,000	605	56.5
Net monthly income	< 1,000 €	217	20.3
	1,000-2,000 €	390	36.4
	2,001-3,000 €	231	21.6
	3,001-4,000 €	90	8.4
	4,001-5,000 €	46	4.3
Purchase frequency	> 5,000€	96	9.0
	Low (< 4 times/year)	172	16.1
	Medium (4-8 times/year)	565	52.8
Level of knowledge of pesticide use in viticulture	High (> 9 times/year)	333	31.1
	No knowledge	168	15.6
	Little knowledge	417	39.0
	Average knowledge	305	28.5
Attitude toward pesticide use	High knowledge	180	16.9
	No concern (indifferent)	194	18.1
	Slight concern	302	28.2
	Moderate concern	226	21.1
	High concern	186	17.4
	Extreme concern	162	15.1

that despite limited knowledge, concern about pesticide use may still play a key role in shaping consumer preferences for organic wines.

To gain a broad overview of the key drivers behind respondents' wine choices, we identified the most important attributes considered

during their most recent organic wine purchase (reference wine). Fig. 4 presents the mean rankings of these attributes, rated on an 11-point Likert scale (-5 = not important, +5 = highly important). The top three factors were taste, organic certification, and production location, whereas alcohol content, vintage, and advertisements were the least important. These trends were consistent across all five countries studied, reflecting similar purchasing motivations among Euro-Mediterranean organic wine consumers. The rankings suggest that sensory qualities and certification play a central role in consumers' most recent organic wine choices.

4.2. Consumer valuation of pesticide-free practices (Hypothesis 1)

The results of the pooled Random Parameters Logit model are presented in Table 4, with coefficients estimated at the sample mean and accompanied by standard errors. The table also reports WTP estimates for each attribute in the choice experiment, along with 95% confidence intervals. The McFadden pseudo R² value of 0.293 indicates a strong model fit, according to Hensher et al. (2015). Although not directly comparable to the R² in OLS regression, values between 0.2 and 0.4 are generally considered indicative of a strongly fitted model in discrete choice studies (Louviere et al., 2000).

The alternative-specific constant is negative and significant, indicating a strong preference for the reference wine—made from 100% pesticide-free grapes—over the hypothetical options with only partial pesticide reduction. Interaction terms between the ASC and country-specific dummy variables (with France as the reference) reveal modest differences in consumer preferences across countries. Compared with their French counterparts, Greek and Italian consumers show a significantly lower preference for partially pesticide-reduced wines. Portuguese consumers display a similar, although statistically insignificant, whereas Spanish consumers show a slight, non-significant preference in the opposite direction. These results suggest that, while some national differences exist, they are not substantial enough to preclude pooling data across countries for analysis.

The attribute coefficients provide further insight into consumer preferences. The positive and significant coefficient for reduced pesticide use confirms its importance in shaping consumer decisions. Certification also plays a critical role: consumers show strong preferences for wines bearing EU-approved third-party certifications, followed by independent third-party labels. In contrast, participatory certifications receive the lowest, statistically insignificant preference, highlighting the value of trusted, institutional certification systems.

The estimated WTP for each 1% reduction in pesticide use is 0.74% of the consumer's average reference price (i.e., the average price paid for

Fig. 4. Mean rank of factors that determined the most recent wine purchased. [The factors were ranked on 7-point Likert scale from 1 = not important to 7= extremely important].

Table 4
Results of the random parameter logit model and consumer willingness to pay.

Attribute	Coefficient β (standard error)	% WTP [95% confidence interval]
<i>Random parameters</i>		
Reduced pesticide use	0.491*** (0.191)	0.74*** [0.18, 1.30]
Participatory certification	5.149 (3.327)	n.a
Independent certification	11.055*** (4.292)	16.70*** [3.99, 29.41]
EU-approved certification	13.571*** (5.269)	20.51*** [4.90, 36.12]
<i>Nonrandom parameters</i>		
Price	-0.662*** (0.257)	
Alternative specific constant (ASC)	-0.611*** (0.237)	
ASC*Greece	-0.452* (0.275)	
ASC*Italy	-0.416** (0.212)	
ASC*Portugal	-0.503 (0.350)	
ASC*Spain	0.252 (0.184)	
<i>Model statistics</i>		
McFadden Pseudo R ²	0.293	
Log-likelihood	-7482.573	
Number of observations	8,560	
Total respondents	1,070	
Average reference price (€/750 ml)	11.79	

***, **, and * represent statistical significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively based on p-values from t-tests; The RPL model was estimated using 500 Halton sequences; [WTP = $-\beta/\beta_{price}$]; n.a = not applicable because the estimated coefficient is not statistically significant. "

their most recently purchased organic wine). Given the average reported reference price of €11.78 for a 750 ml bottle, this implies that approximately €8.84 of the average price is attributable to the 100% pesticide-free attribute of their reference organic wine.

In terms of certification premiums, EU-approved third-party labels command a 20.5% premium, whereas independent third-party certifications earn a 16.7% premium. Participatory certification adds little to no monetary value to consumers' choices. These findings reinforce the importance of formal, trusted certifications in organic wine markets.

Overall, the results support Hypothesis 1: consumers place high value on reduced pesticide use in organic wine, with a WTP of 0.74% per unit percentage reduction. Combined with the premium attributed to EU

Table 5
Country-specific Random Parameter Logit models with WTP estimates.

Variables	France	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Spain
Reduced pesticide use (RP)	0.375*** (0.146)	0.440*** (0.171)	0.362*** (0.141)	0.453*** (0.176)	0.391*** (0.152)
Participatory certification (PC)	5.204* (3.164)	-4.011 (2.438)	-3.033 (1.844)	-5.108 (3.105)	-4.283*** (1.663)
Independent certification (IC)	7.368*** (2.86)	8.070 (4.906)	6.151** (3.138)	7.136 (4.338)	6.045 (3.675)
EU-approved certification (EC)	10.06 (6.116)	11.613*** (4.508)	9.395*** (3.647)	10.905*** (4.233)	12.435*** (4.827)
Price	-0.575*** (0.223)	-0.614*** (0.238)	-0.505* (0.307)	-0.707*** (0.274)	-0.671*** (0.26)
Alternative specific constant (ASC)	-0.825*** (0.32)	-0.159* (0.097)	-0.831*** (0.323)	0.633*** (0.246)	1.470*** (0.571)
Willingness to pay as a percentage of previous price					
WTP_RP	0.651	0.717	0.718	0.641	0.583
WTP_PC	9.050	n.a	n.a	n.a	-6.383
WTP_IC	12.814	n.a	12.180	n.a	n.a
WTP_EC	n.a	18.914	18.604	15.424	18.531
Model fit statistics					
McFadden Pseudo R ²	0.168	0.160	0.147	0.204	0.186
Log-likelihood	-2055.527	-2162.069	-2143.696	-552.491	-1196.391
Number of observations	2248	1968	2288	632	1416
Total respondents	281	246	286	79	177
Average reference price (€/750 ml)	€13.60	€9.64	€13.04	€10.77	€11.90

***, **, and * represent statistical significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively based on p-values from t-tests; The RPL model was estimated using 500 Halton sequences; [% WTP = $-\beta/\beta_{price}$]; n.a. = not applicable because the estimated coefficient is not statistically significant. "

certification, the total consumer WTP for a pesticide-free, certified organic wine approaches 95% of the average price of the reference organic wines. This underscores the central role of pesticide-free production and trusted certification as defining features of consumer value in the organic wine market.

4.3. Differences across countries

The country-specific RPL models, presented in Table 5, reveal notable differences in consumer preferences across the five Euro-Mediterranean countries. As in the pooled results, the coefficient of reduced pesticide use is positively significant in all countries, although the strength of preference varies—highest in Portugal and lowest in Greece. With respect to certification, preferences are largely consistent across countries. Compared with no certification, participatory certification is the least preferred among the three categories: it is positively significant in France; negatively significant in Spain; and not significant in Italy, Greece, or Portugal. Independent third-party certification shows attract moderate preference and it is statistically significant in France, Italy, and Greece, but it is not Portugal or Spain. Consistent with the pooled model, EU-approved third-party certification is the most preferred, with positive and significant coefficients in Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain but not in France. The price coefficients are negative, as expected, and statistically significant in all countries, with Portugal exhibiting the highest sensitivity and Italy the lowest. The alternative-specific constant is negative in France, Italy, and Greece but positive in Portugal and Spain, indicating variation in consumer preferences for the hypothetical wines due to unobserved factors beyond the specified attributes.

The country-specific WTP estimates reveal both shared patterns and differences in how consumers value sustainability attributes in wine relative to the average market price of their reference wine. All countries show a positive WTP for reduced pesticide use, with Italy and Greece having the highest valuations and Spain the lowest. For example, Italian consumers are willing to pay 0.72% of their average reference price for each unit reduction in pesticide use, whereas Spanish consumers are willing to pay 0.58%. This implies that full pesticide elimination accounts for 75% and 58% of the premium that consumers are willing to pay for organic wine in Italy and Spain, respectively.

With regard to certification, only French consumers show a positive and significant WTP for participatory certification, whereas Spanish consumers assign it a negative premium. The estimates are not significant in the other three countries. Independent certification elicits a positive WTP in France and Italy, reflecting consumer trust in third-party verification, but it is not significant in the remaining countries.

EU-approved certification commands a substantial WTP premium in Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain—exceeding 15% of the average reference price in each case—but is not significant in France. These patterns highlight the heterogeneity in consumer valuation of certification types and environmentally friendly practices across the five countries.

4.4. Segmentation in consumers of organic wine (Hypotheses 2 and 3)

The results from the latent class model supported Hypothesis 2, which posited the existence of distinct segments among organic consumers based on their preferences and valuation of pesticide-free attributes in organic wine production. Fig. 5 presents the elbow plot of the BIC statistics for class models ranging from 1 to 10 solutions. The plot indicates that the optimal number of classes is three, as further increases beyond this point yield minimal improvements in the BIC values. A similar pattern is observed with the AIC, confirming the robustness of the class solution determined by the LCM. Additionally, the McFadden R² value of 0.321 falls within the acceptable range for goodness-of-fit in choice models, further validating the results.

Table 6 presents the latent class results with marginal probabilities at the 95% confidence level. The majority of organic wine consumers belong to Class 1 (66%), followed by Class 2 (22%) and Class 3 (12%). For Class 1, the coefficients for pesticide avoidance, price, and all certification types, with the exception of participatory certification, are statistically significant. The ASC value indicates that consumers in Class 1 generally prefer the reference wine (i.e., organic with 100% pesticide reduction) over the hypothetical options (i.e., wines with incremental pesticide reduction), which aligns with the RPL results for the full sample. The estimated WTP for pesticide reduction among this segment represents 81% of the average price for a 100% pesticide-free organic wine or 0.81% for each percentage reduction in the volume of pesticide use. The consumers in this segment also show similar valuations for different certification bodies, placing the highest premium on EU-approved third-party certification, followed by independent third-party certification, with the coefficient for participatory certification not statistically significant.

For Class 2, the coefficients of all the attributes are statistically significant except for price, which has the expected negative sign but is non-significant. Similarly, the ASC value for this class suggests that consumers in this segment prefer wines with 100% pesticide-free organic grapes to those with partial pesticide reduction. The coefficients of all the certification types were significant, with the highest preference for the EC and a negative preference for the PC. Although the

Table 6
Latent class model showing the three identified consumer segments.

Attribute	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3
Reduced pesticide use (RP)	0.381*** (0.148)	0.288** (0.147)	0.101* (0.061)
Participatory certification (PC)	4.612 (3.651)	5.732* (3.481)	1.982 (1.263)
Independent certification (IC)	9.835* (5.879)	13.442** (6.848)	3.652* (2.214)
EU-approved certification (EC)	10.187** (5.187)	16.114*** (6.216)	5.124** (2.514)
Price	-0.603* (0.358)	-0.734 (0.631)	-0.842*** (0.315)
ASC	-0.472** (0.231)	-0.589* (0.352)	0.702** (0.358)
WTP_RP (%)	0.81**	n.a	0.12**
WTP_PC (%)	9.77	n.a	7.73
WTP_IC (%)	20.84	a.a	6.71*
WTP_EC (%)	21.58**	n.a	13.21*
Class probability	0.664 [0.628, 0.701]	0.216 [0.183, 0.249]	0.120 [0.099, 0.140]
Log-likelihood	-6562.539		
McFadden Pseudo R ²	0.321		
Sample (n)	1,070		

***, *, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively, based on p-values from t-tests. Standard errors are shown in parentheses. 'n.a.' denotes cases where the price coefficient is not statistically significant."

estimated WTP for pesticide reduction represents approximately 39% of the average reference price, it cannot be reliably interpreted as a monetary value since the coefficient of the price attribute is not statistically significant.

Class 3 is characterized by a large coefficient of the price attribute, which is also highly significant (1% level of significance). Only two certification types are significant, i.e., IC and EC, at the 10% and 5% significance levels, respectively. In contrast to Classes 1 and 2, the ASC is positive and significant at the 5% level, suggesting that consumers in this class segment are willing to switch from 100% pesticide-free reference organic wines to hypothetical wines with partial levels of pesticide reduction. The estimated WTP for pesticide reduction represents approximately 12% of the average reference price.

Overall, the LCM result reveals three distinct consumer segments, confirming *hypotheses 2 and 3* of the study. The consumers in segment 1 place the highest value on pesticide avoidance but show relatively lower sensitivity to certification types and price levels. In Segment 2, consumers emphasize certification, particularly EU-approved and

Fig. 5. Elbow method using Bayesian information criteria values from the maximum likelihood estimation of up to 10 class solutions. [The ideal number of classes is at the elbow point, where adding more classes provides little additional benefit in model fit].

independent certifications, reflecting strong trust in recognized certification bodies while maintaining moderate sensitivity to price and pesticide avoidance. Those in segment 3, on the other hand, place the least emphasis on certification and pesticide avoidance, prioritizing price over other wine attributes.

We did not include the coefficients of the interaction terms between ASC and country-specific dummies in Table 6 because they were not statistically significant for the three latent classes identified.

4.5. Characteristics of the consumer segments (Hypothesis 3)

Table 7 presents the characteristics of the three latent classes in detail. Specifically, we investigated class membership on the basis of subjective knowledge of pesticide use in winegrowing, attitudes toward pesticide use, and sociodemographic factors, by computing posterior class probabilities. These probabilities were then used to assign each respondent to the class with the highest likelihood.

Based on each consumer’s assigned class, which is determined by posterior probabilities, we analyzed the reported characteristics of each latent class. Our analysis suggests that Class 1 could be described as awareness- or concern-driven. Membership in this class is strongly associated with high subjective knowledge and high to extreme concern about pesticide use in winegrowing. As shown in Fig. 6, the distribution of subjective knowledge levels regarding pesticide use varies across the three latent classes. Class 1 has an increasing probability of membership as knowledge levels rise, indicating that individuals with greater knowledge are more likely to belong to this group. In contrast, Class 3 shows a consistent decline, suggesting that consumers with less knowledge are more likely to be in this class. For example, 18% of consumers in Class 3 reported no knowledge of pesticide use, whereas only 9% in this class reported a high level of knowledge, illustrating the decreasing likelihood of Class 3 membership as knowledge increases. Class 2 fluctuates slightly, peaking at low knowledge levels before gradually declining at higher knowledge levels.

For Class 2, the likelihood of membership on the basis of knowledge and attitudinal variables shows mixed patterns, with average levels across each variable. However, according to the LCM results, Class 2 is best characterized as certification-trusting. As noted in Table 5, the

Table 7
Class membership based on knowledge, attitudes and sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents.

Characteristics/ Variable	Class 1 Awareness-driven	Class 2 Certification- trusting	Class 3 Price-sensitive
Knowledge of pesticide use	High level	Medium	Low
Attitude toward pesticide use	High to extreme concern	Moderate concern	Slight concern
Average reference price (€)	13.80	11.21	9.85
Gender	Majority are male	Nearly equal	Majority are female
Age	Majority are between 35 and 55 years	Majority are 55+	Majority are between 25 and 34 years
Income level	Medium	High	Low
Place of residence	Majority in cities < 50,000 residents	Equal distribution	Majority in cities >50,000 residents
Country	Majority in France and Spain	Majority in Greece and Italy	Majority in Greece and Portugal

Note: Class membership was determined using posterior probability estimates, assigning each consumer to the class with the highest probability. Crosstabulations were conducted to examine how all the characteristics varied across the classes. The variables were not included as direct covariates in the LCM to allow latent class segmentation to emerge purely from choice behavior, avoiding potential biases introduced by predefined classifications.

coefficients for all the certification types included in the choice design are statistically significant. Consumers in this class exhibit a strong preference for EU-approved third-party certification, followed by independent third-party certification, while expressing dissatisfaction with certification issued by first- or second-party participatory bodies.

On the other hand, Class 3 could be described as price-driven or price-sensitive. The LCM results reveal that price has a highly significant and negative effect on choice for this segment, more so than in the other two classes. The consumers in Class 3 are highly sensitive to price, with higher-priced alternatives being less likely to be chosen. Notably, it is the only class that demonstrates a stronger preference for hypothetical wines with incremental pesticide reduction (i.e., ASC is positive), potentially due to their lower prices compared to the most recently purchased wine (reference). Additionally, members of this class report the lowest average reference price and exhibit the least concern with respect to pesticide use in winegrowing.

In terms of sociodemographic characteristics, Class 1 primarily consists of middle-aged, middle-income male consumers, predominantly living in smaller cities (fewer than 50,000 inhabitants), especially in France and Spain. Class 2 is evenly distributed between males and females, with younger, lower-income consumers predominantly in Greece and Italy residing equally in larger and smaller cities. In contrast, Class 3 is mainly composed of females under 35 years of age, with low incomes and a greater likelihood of living in larger cities, particularly in Greece and Portugal.

5. Discussion

This study aimed to assess the extent to which reduced synthetic pesticide use—a key component of organic winegrowing—contributes to the price premium consumers are willing to pay. It also sought to identify distinct consumer segments based on their valuation of pesticide-free practices and to explore how these segments differ in preferences and personal traits. The results from the random parameter logit and latent class models provide strong support for the hypotheses. Reduced pesticide use explains a significant share of the organic wine premium, echoing Di Vita et al. (2019), who found environmental concerns drive consumer choices. Moreover, three consumer classes emerged: awareness-driven, certification-trusting, and price-sensitive. These findings, which are comparable to previous studies, underscore the varied motivations shaping preferences for organic wine and offer implications for sustainable pesticide use, policy, and EU wine market strategies.

5.1. Consumer valuation of reduced pesticide use

Previous studies have shown that consumers are willing to pay a premium for sustainably produced wines, especially organic wines (Boncinelli et al., 2021; Sellers-Rubio & Nicolau-Gonzalbez, 2016a). Compared with conventional wines, organic wines have been found to command a premium of 13% to 40%, depending on the region and valuation method used (Scozzafava et al., 2021; Vecchio et al., 2023). The key drivers of this premium include health and environmental concerns, curiosity and pro-organic attitudes (Bonn et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2022). However, these drivers are often treated holistically, with a limited understanding of the specific contribution of production practices such as reduced pesticide use—one of the defining features of organic wine production.

This study revealed that up to 74% of the premium for organic wine could be attributed to pesticide-free grape cultivation. When combined with certification from an EU-approved third-party regulator, this figure increases to approximately 95% of the average price that consumers are willing to pay for organic wines. The combined effects demonstrate that consumers place a significant premium on certification and pesticide-free winegrapes, although grapes undergo several processing steps before becoming wine.

Fig. 6. Distribution of class membership based on consumers' subjective knowledge of pesticide use.

The substantial combined premium may be explained by the signaling power of certification. Certification not only assures consumers of the absence of synthetic pesticides but also signals other desirable credence attributes, such as environmental sustainability, quality, and adherence to oenological standards (Auriol & Schilizzi, 2015; Holland, 2016). In this way, it serves as a trust-enhancing mechanism that consolidates multiple hidden product characteristics into a single, reliable label. The premium attributed to the combined effects of the two may therefore reflect the holistic value that consumers assign to certified organic wines, encompassing health, environmental, and quality expectations. Additionally, the high premium could be due to potential non-attendance to the price attribute, as suggested by Campbell et al. (2011). Thus, because the hypothetical wine options were priced lower than the respondents' reference wine, some consumers may have ignored price altogether, resulting in a lower estimated price coefficient and, consequently, higher WTP estimates.

5.2. Comparison with existing findings on WTP for pesticide-free and organic products

Previous research has shown that consumers are willing to pay 5% to 20% more for pesticide-free fresh foods, such as fruits and vegetables (Boccaletti & Nardella, 2000; Hayati et al., 2017). While our study does not estimate WTP for pesticide-free wine directly, it sheds light on the proportion of the organic premium driven by pesticide-free cultivation. This provides valuable insight into consumer preferences for a key credence attribute, extending the literature beyond unprocessed products to include processed foods.

Despite the heavy reliance on pesticides in the production of several raw materials used in processed foods, only a few studies have analyzed consumers' WTP for pesticide reduction in such products (Gatti et al., 2022; Larvoe et al., 2025; Nitzko et al., 2024b). Nitzko et al. (2024) reported that consumers are willing to pay approximately 60% more for pesticide-free wheat rolls, while Larvoe et al. (2025) reported a 24% premium for extra virgin olive oil produced with 40% fewer pesticides. Gatti et al. (2022) estimated a US\$3.60 premium for pesticide-free coffee and US\$5.80 premium for organic coffee, indicating that approximately 62% of the organic premium is attributable to the pesticide-free attribute.

Comparing the results of this study with these previous findings offers three key insights. First, the WTP for pesticide-free wheat rolls and coffee aligns closely with the 74% value estimated in this study for

organic wine. Although the olive oil premium appears lower, extrapolating the 24% premium for 40% pesticide reduction to a 100% pesticide-free scenario yields a comparable estimate. This suggests that consumers consistently place a high premium on pesticide-free practices across diverse product categories.

Second, discrepancies in WTP estimates could partly be explained by methodological differences. Most previous studies relied on contingent valuation or traditional choice experiments, whereas this study employed a discrete choice experiment tied to consumers' most recent organic wine purchases. This provides a more realistic baseline, making the estimation of consumers' valuation more reliable (Ho et al., 2024; Kilders & Caputo, 2024).

Third, while product-specific features and contextual factors may have influenced differences in premiums for reduced pesticide use to some extent, the study confirms our hypothesis that pesticide reduction accounts for a significant share of the organic wine premium—more than any other organic requirement. This suggests that pesticide-free cultivation may be the primary driver of consumer preference for many organic processed products, even though it is often overshadowed by broader health and environmental concerns. This finding underscores a valuable opportunity for eco-labels to explicitly highlight levels of pesticide use in a transparent manner to enhance consumer engagement and product preferences.

With regard to segmentation, although all the study participants had purchased organic wine previously, their valuations of pesticide reduction varied. For the majority, awareness of pesticide use was a decisive factor—consistent with earlier findings linking environmental and health awareness to higher WTP (Boncinelli et al., 2021; Ogbeide et al., 2015). The three identified consumer segments align with those in a recent study by Zanchini et al. (2024), who reported similar clusters in the broader wine market: higher-priced and nation-specific wine seekers, certification seekers and price-sensitive consumers. Awareness-driven consumers and high-price seekers prioritize sustainability and authenticity, certification-trusting consumers seek assurance through labeling, and price-sensitive consumers emphasize affordability regardless of the production method.

5.3. Variations across countries

The country-specific RPL and WTP estimates reveal how consumers in France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain value sustainability attributes in organic wine in ways that reflect their unique cultural,

institutional, and market contexts (Zanchini et al., 2024). Although reduced pesticide use is positively valued across all five countries, its strength varies—being highest in Portugal and lowest in Greece—likely due to differences in environmental awareness and consumer experience with sustainable practices.

Certification preferences reveal deeper trust dynamics: French consumers uniquely value participatory certification, perhaps due to stronger civic networks and trust in local producer systems. In contrast, Spanish consumers attach a negative premium to participatory schemes, indicating skepticism toward informal oversight. The broad preference for EU-approved certification in Southern European countries (except France) likely reflects a greater reliance on external quality assurance in contexts with weaker domestic regulatory traditions. France's relative indifference may stem from a robust national certification infrastructure and a more informed consumer base.

Price sensitivity also varies significantly: Portuguese consumers are the most price sensitive, whereas Italians are the least price sensitive—likely reflecting both income disparities and the cultural centrality of wine in Italy, where consumers are more willing to pay for perceived quality. These findings align with those of previous studies, emphasizing how consumer valuation of sustainable wine attributes is shaped by institutional trust, national identity and socioeconomic factors (Krystallis et al., 2006; Rahmani et al., 2019; Vecchio, Toccaceli, et al., 2023; Zanchini et al., 2024).

5.4. Theoretical implications

This study contributes to the literature on consumer behavior and sustainable food systems by offering a dynamic approach to valuing a specific production attribute—pesticide avoidance—within an already certified organic product. By isolating the value that consumers place on pesticide-free cultivation within organic wine, this study enhances our understanding of how credence attributes influence WTP. Unlike most prior studies that examine organic labels as undifferentiated bundles of attributes (Maesano et al., 2021; Schäufele and Hamm, 2018; Vecchio et al., 2023), this study disaggregated one core attribute and quantified its contribution to the total premium. This disaggregation advances theoretical frameworks on credence goods, signaling theory, and behavioral economics by demonstrating that not all organic attributes carry equal weight in consumer valuation. In particular, reduced pesticide use accounts for a substantial share of the organic premium, although its importance may be shadowed by broader concerns related to health and environmental sustainability.

Second, this study advances the understanding of how consumers value different certification schemes in the wine industry. While previous research highlights the importance of certification in driving sustainable choices, it often assumes that all certifications signal sustainability equally (Alonso Ugaglia et al., 2021; Mazzocchi et al., 2019). Our findings challenge this assumption by showing that the source of certification matters—schemes backed by trusted institutions are more effective in eliciting a sustainability premium from wine consumers.

Moreover, by integrating consumer segmentation with attribute-specific WTP, the findings align with and extend theories of heterogeneous consumer preferences in sustainability contexts. The identification of distinct latent classes—each with different motivations, trust mechanisms, and trade-offs—offers deeper insights into the role of values, knowledge, and certification trust in shaping consumer choices.

Finally, incorporating data from five Euro-Mediterranean countries, this study provides theoretical insights into how cultural, institutional, and economic contexts shape consumer preferences for credence attributes. The variation in WTP for pesticide reduction and certification highlights the context-dependent nature of signaling effectiveness and consumer trust. This cross-national perspective offers a more grounded understanding of how credence goods are valued in diverse market settings.

5.5. Practical implications

The findings have several practical implications for producers, policymakers, and market strategists in the wine sector and beyond. For producers—especially conventional winegrowers—the high premium that consumers attach to pesticide-free attributes presents a compelling incentive to adopt pesticide-reducing practices without necessarily pursuing full organic certification. While the European Commission aims to expand organic farming to 25% agricultural land by 2030, organic production remains costly and complex. Yields are typically 80% of conventional levels, and producing a bottle of organic wine could cost at least 50% more due to certification fees and increased labor for tasks such as manual weeding and pest control (de la Cruz et al., 2023; de Ponti et al., 2012; Negro et al., 2015; Scozzafava et al., 2021). These barriers often deter smaller vineyards from transitioning into fully organic status. However, the significant price premium for pesticide-free practices suggests that conventional producers could still capture much of the organic premium through incremental sustainability efforts—offering a more flexible and inclusive path toward sustainable EU viticulture.

For certification bodies and policymakers, these results highlight the potential value of labeling schemes that indicate levels of pesticide use rather than relying on binary organic/conventional distinctions. Such differentiated labels could promote transparency while rewarding producers for gradual improvements.

For marketers, the segmentation findings call for targeted messaging: environmentally friendly cultivation and transparency should be emphasized for awareness-driven consumers, while EU certification signals could build stronger trust among more institutional-trusting segments. Price-sensitive consumers may respond better to targeted incentives or discounts that increase access to sustainably produced wines.

Finally, the dynamic reference-dependent choice approach—used to estimate the value of a single sustainability practice within a bundled product—provides a useful model for future research in food and beverage markets, where credence attributes are difficult to isolate.

5.6. Limitations and future research

While this study achieves its primary objectives, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, despite mitigation measures such as solemn oaths and cheap talk scripts, stated preference methods remain susceptible to hypothetical and social desirability biases. Organic wine consumers, in particular, may respond in ways that align with socially accepted norms, potentially inflating the estimated premium for pesticide-free attributes. Future studies could adopt incentive-compatible approaches—such as real purchase simulations or experimental auctions—to capture actual behavior and market responses. Additionally, big data analytics and machine learning could be employed to uncover latent preferences from observed consumer actions.

Second, sampling consumers across five countries provided valuable cross-national insights but may have broadened the reference points used in the pooled model, potentially masking or inflating the estimated premiums attached to specific attributes. Although a country-specific analysis was conducted, unbalanced data—particularly the limited sample sizes for some countries—may have weakened the robustness of cross-country comparisons. Future research could use equally large and representative samples across countries to allow for more reliable cross-cultural analysis.

Third, while online surveys facilitate broad and stratified sampling, they may underrepresent individuals with limited internet access or digital literacy—typically older, rural, or lower-income populations. As a result, the findings primarily reflect the preferences of digitally active consumers. Moreover, since the sampling frame was limited to consumers who had previously purchased organic wine and were reachable

through specific digital channels, the generalizability of the results may be constrained. Although we employed stratified quota sampling based on key demographics to enhance representativeness, the non-probability nature of web-based sampling may still introduce socio-demographic biases and limit the extent to which findings can be extrapolated to the broader population of organic wine consumers. Future studies could adopt mixed-mode data collection strategies, including in-person or telephone surveys, to improve inclusivity and generalizability.

Furthermore, although the dynamic reference price-dependent design helps to consider attributes of interest while holding others constant, it may have inadvertently overemphasized their perceived importance. Additionally, the design did not explicitly address attribute non-attendance—where respondents disregard certain attributes when making their choices. If some participants disproportionately focused on the pesticide-free claim, premium estimates could be biased. Future research should consider using stated or inferred ANA models to correct for such potential biases and enhance the validity of real-world trade-offs.

Finally, this study concentrates on vineyard-level practices. Future research could explore consumer valuation of oenological restrictions during the winemaking process—such as the non-use of chemical additives and the limited use of sulphites. Examining these alongside viticulture practices would offer a more holistic understanding of consumer preferences in the organic wine market.

6. Conclusions

In this study, we analyze how consumers value the limited use of synthetic pesticides in organic wine production and estimate their willingness to pay for this core practice as a proportion of their previous organic wine price. Using a reference price-dependent choice experiment by sampling organic consumers across five Euro-Mediterranean countries, we find that up to 74% of the average price paid for the organic wines previously purchased by the sampled consumers is attributable to pesticide-free practices, with this proportion increasing when accompanied by certification, particularly an EU-approved third-party certification. The findings reveal three distinct consumer segments—*awareness-driven*, *certification-trusting*, and *price-sensitive*—each influenced by different motivations in the selection of organic wines. This segmentation underscores the importance of targeted marketing strategies and the role of certification in reinforcing consumer trust. Additionally, the results point to the existence of market incentives for conventional winegrowers willing to adopt pesticide-free or low-pesticide practices without requiring full organic certification, potentially bridging the gap between conventional and organic wine production. Overall, the findings highlight strong consumer preference for reduced pesticide use and its significant influence on their WTP for organic wines. By leveraging certification and transparent labeling information, stakeholders in the wine industry could cater to consumer preferences for reduced pesticide use while promoting environmentally sustainable viticulture.

Ethical statement

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical research guidelines for human subjects. All participants in our survey provided informed consent after receiving a thorough explanation of the study's objectives. Participation was entirely voluntary, with respondents having the right to withdraw at any time without consequences. Personally identifiable information was carefully protected to ensure participants' anonymity and confidentiality.

The research protocol including the survey instrument was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Centre for Agro-Food Economy and Development (CREDA) under approval number 020-2024. This study complies with the ethical standards set forth in the Declaration of Helsinki and the European General Data Protection

Regulation (GDPR).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Noah Larvoe: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zein Kallas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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